

Iatrogenic Allogenesia and ASIA Syndrome Associated with Cutaneous Mucormycosis. Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Iatrogenic allogenesia is a disease characterized by nonspecific clinical and serological alterations at the local and systemic levels, with a nonspecific pattern of recurrence. Asia syndrome presents with classic constitutional manifestations including myalgia, arthralgia, chronic fatigue, and dry mouth, as well as neurological manifestations such as cognitive alterations, memory loss, and neurological disabilities.

Clinical case: A 43-year-old woman with a history of unspecified biopolymer application to the face, breasts, and buttocks in 2013, unspecified paranasal sinus surgery in 2015 due to complications from biopolymer application, which caused soft tissue infection due to iatrogenic allogenesia, development of ASIA syndrome, and cutaneous mucormycosis. Subsequent septic shock, leading to death.

Discussion: The therapeutic approach to this type of pathology is complex due to the various anatomical areas in which the modeling material infiltrates and the different techniques used. Mucormycosis is a rare disease, difficult to diagnose, with high morbidity and mortality. Diagnosis is often delayed, and the disease tends to progress rapidly. There are reports of cutaneous mucormycosis and also necrotizing fasciitis in immunocompetent patients. Cutaneous mucormycosis in young adult patients is uncommon, has unusual clinical presentation, and should be suspected in previously established skin lesions exposed to any contaminated substances or objects.

Conclusions: The use of biopolymers in Mexico is a public health problem that has been increasing over the years and must be eradicated and its complications treated in a timely manner.

KEYWORDS: Biopolymers. Iatrogenic allogenesia. ASIA syndrome. Cutaneous mucormycosis.

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INTRODUCTION

Biopolymers are inert substances, most of which are silicone derivatives such as polyvinyl methacrylate or polymethyl siloxane, and may include other materials such as methacrylate or collagen [1,2].

However, biopolymers have weak mechanical properties and durability compared to synthetic polymers. Furthermore, with the exception of chitosan, biopolymers do not have

antimicrobial properties to counteract the proliferation of microorganisms in their applications [3].

Although the synthesis of biopolymers consumes chemical energy and nutrients, it is maintained by bacteria, as biopolymers allow them to persist and grow in a wide range of often unfavorable conditions, including exposure to host immune responses during infection [4].

The tissue reaction to the infiltration of this type of product can be acute or even delayed [1]. The risks of using these

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substances can cause the body to reject the injected substance, leading to infection, tissue necrosis, sterile abscesses, and autoimmune responses. The sequelae can occur 10, 20, and even 30 years after application [5].

Below we present the case of a 43-year-old female with soft tissue infection due to iatrogenic allogenesia, development of ASIA syndrome, and cutaneous mucormycosis.

CLINICAL CASE

A 43-year-old woman with a history of unspecified biopolymer application to the face, breasts, and buttocks in 2013, and unspecified paranasal sinus surgery in 2015 due to complications from biopolymer application. After the

procedure, the patient continued to have problems with facial edema and multiple hospitalizations due to this complication, which was treated with unspecified medical management.

Two months prior to hospitalization, the patient presented with progressive increase in facial edema with difficulty opening her eyes, respiratory distress, dry mouth (Figure 1 A and B), difficulty swallowing, asthenia, adynamia, myalgia, fatigue, edema in the thoracic and pelvic limbs, progressive weakness of the extremities, ecchymotic lesions on the hands, forearms, and feet (Figure 2 A and B), an ulcerated lesion on the right buttock measuring approximately 20 cm (Figure 3), and hyperpigmented lesions on both mammary glands (Figure 4).

Figure 1. Local and systemic involvement caused by adjuvant substance. A) Angioedema and facial ecchymosis, associated with ecchymosis on the forearms and hands. B) Physical deterioration, angioedema, and facial ecchymosis with dry mouth.

Figure 2. A) Bruising on the right forearm. B) Bruising and swelling on the right foot.

Figure 3. Allogenes ulcer in the right gluteal region.

Figure 4. Local complication due to adjuvant substance. A) Hyperpigmented and hyperkeratotic lesions on both breasts due to iatrogenic allogenes. B) Lesion due to iatrogenic allogenes on the right breast.

She was admitted to the emergency department with the aforementioned injuries, as well as altered mental status, dyspnea on moderate exertion, increased respiratory rate, decreased body temperature, and hypotension, for which vasopressors were administered, stabilizing the patient. Laboratory tests were performed upon admission to the emergency room, which reported the following: leukocytes 6.3, erythrocytes 4.8, hemoglobin 13.9, hematocrit 43.9, mean corpuscular volume 90.9, mean corpuscular hemoglobin 28.8, platelets 101,000, glucose 96.4, urea 26.5, BUN 12, creatinine 0.57, alkaline phosphatase 151, lactate dehydrogenase 821, calcium 7.69, phosphate 3.17, chloride 99.2, potassium 4.96, sodium 130, magnesium 1.71.

He began his hospital stay under the care of the surgery department in conjunction with internal medicine. Treatment began with parenteral hydration, vasopressors, analgesics, antiemetics, diuretics, and broad-spectrum antibiotics. A study protocol was initiated, and five days after hospitalization, serological tests were performed, which

reported: Anti-native DNA antibodies (-), Anti-Centromere Antibodies (-), Anti-SSA/Ro Antibodies (+), Anti-SSB/La Antibodies (-), Anti-Sm Antibodies (-), Anti-SCL Antibodies (-), pANCA (-), C3 < 40mg/dL (Low), C4 8.2mg/dL (Low), Anti-RNP Antibodies (+).

An assessment was carried out by the rheumatology and surgery departments, which concluded, based on clinical and serological data, that the diagnoses of SLE, nonspecific inflammatory myopathy, and scleroderma could have been triggered by the history of external agent application 10 years ago (iatrogenic allogenes). An abdominal ultrasound was requested, which reported mild hepatomegaly and minimal free intra-abdominal fluid. A culture was taken from the gluteal ulcer, which reported abundant growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and treatment with cefepime was indicated. Three weeks after admission, surgical cleaning of the ulcer was performed, and she continued her hospital stay with wound care, adding topical rifocin-based antibiotic and methylprednisolone boluses, showing improvement in vasculitic lesions.

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The patient developed mixed delirium, and non-pharmacological measures and treatment with atypical antipsychotics were initiated. In addition to non-active bleeding in the right nostril, the oral cavity showed missing teeth, hyperemic and inflamed gums without purulent secretion, facial swelling with increased volume, and hyperemia. A soft palate biopsy was performed, reporting acute and chronic inflammatory reaction associated with mucormycosis, negative for malignancy, and amphotericin B deoxycholate was initiated.

A biopsy of the gluteal fat was taken, revealing soft tissue with chronic granulomatous inflammation of the foreign body

type and dystrophic calcifications, negative for bacilli. The diagnosis was adjuvant-induced autoimmune inflammatory syndrome (ASIA), meeting three major criteria and two minor criteria based on the ASIA diagnostic criteria proposed by Shoenfeld and Agmon-Levin. Due to the symptoms and biopsy taken from the palate, a cranial CT scan was performed, which reported soft tissue cellulitis at the level of the facial bone with increased volume and density, multiple inflammatory-looking lymph nodes in the masticatory spaces (Figure 5). There was no evidence of fracture or perforation of the soft palate or chronic right mastoiditis.

Figure 5. Cranial CT scan: Soft tissue inflammation in the right facial bone.

In July 2023, the patient suffered cardiorespiratory arrest, requiring advanced life support maneuvers, including endotracheal intubation and cardiopulmonary resuscitation, which led to spontaneous resuscitation. Subsequently, mechanical ventilation and vasopressor support were required. Three days after the cardiorespiratory arrest, the patient presented with cardiac arrhythmia, which progressed to cardiorespiratory arrest. Resuscitation efforts were performed without achieving spontaneous circulation recovery, corroborated by an electrocardiogram showing an isoelectric trace.

DISCUSSION

In 2008, Coiffman coined the term “iatrogenic allogeneic” to describe this disease: allogeneic because it is caused by substances foreign to the body, and iatrogenic because it is caused by doctors or people who inject these substances [6]. The disease is characterized by nonspecific clinical and serological alterations at the local and systemic levels, with a nonspecific pattern of recurrence. The clinical presentation can vary in both symptoms and severity [6].

Its clinical manifestations can occur between six hours and 30 years after application and include a large number of manifestations, both local and systemic, which can range from mild changes to deformity and multiple organ failure [7]. The most common manifestations are lumps,

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depressions, and irregularities, pain, ecchymosis or hematoma, overcorrection, long-term scarring, inflammation, skin irregularities, edema, erythema, hyperpigmentation or hyperpigmentations, ulcerations, hardening, necrosis, and fistulas, generally systemic symptoms, especially joint manifestations, as well as myalgia, polyarthritis, Raynaud's phenomenon, and autoimmune diseases [2, 8].

Peña Restrepo et al. report that in the last decade, there have been 358 cases of iatrogenic allogeneic per 1,000 patients using bioimplants, 97% of whom are women [8]. At present, the true incidence and prevalence are unknown, but it is likely to become a public health problem in the near future [5]. Biopolymers have been recognized as adjuvants that trigger

ASIA syndrome, as they form part of the “autoimmune ecology” [9].

In 2011, Shoenfeld and Agmon-Levin introduced the term ASIA (Autoimmune [Auto-inflammatory] Syndrome Induced by Adjuvants) [5]. In 2011, Levin proposed 12 major and minor criteria for establishing the diagnosis of ASIA, requiring confirmation of two major criteria or one major and two minor criteria [10]. At the end of 2014, Alijotas-Reig proposed new criteria for establishing the diagnosis of ASIA; although these mostly coincide with those proposed by Levin, a minimum latency period and confirmation of additional immunological markers are established (Table 1) [10].

A) ASIA diagnostic criteria proposed by Shoenfeld & Agmon-Levin	B) New diagnostic criteria for human adjuvant disease (ASIA) proposed by Alijotas-Reig
<p>Major criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to an external stimulus (infection, vaccine, silicone, adjuvant) prior to onset of manifestations. <p>Onset of typical clinical features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement after removal of the triggering agent. • Biopsy with typical findings in the involved organs. 	<p>Major criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to an external stimulus— biomaterials, vaccines, anilines, or other organic/inorganic materials—before onset of clinical manifestations. • Minimum latency of days (1–2 weeks) for vaccines; about one month when the trigger is not a vaccine (e.g., biomaterials). <p>Clinical manifestations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local/regional: inflammatory nodules; cutaneous edema or angioedema; cutaneous induration; pseudo-abscesses; lymphadenopathy; morphea-like panniculitis; sarcoid-like lesions. • Systemic: distant inflammatory nodules; arthritis; sicca complex/Sjögren syndrome; myositis or muscle weakness; extensive panniculitis; demyelinating neurologic syndromes. • Progression to a systemic or organ-specific autoimmune disease. • Biopsy of the involved area or lymph nodes showing foreign-body features, or histopathologic findings consistent with autoimmune/granulomatous diseases. • Improvement after removal of the triggering agent. • Compatible HLA types (e.g., HLA-B8, HLA-DRB1, HLA-DR3, HLA-DQB1, or haplotype combinations).
<p>Minor criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appearance of autoantibodies or antibodies directed against the implicated adjuvant. • Other clinical manifestations (e.g., irritable bowel syndrome). • Specific HLA types (e.g., HLA-DRB1, HLA-DQB1). • Evolution to an autoimmune disease (e.g., multiple sclerosis, systemic sclerosis). 	<p>Minor criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recent history of triggering factors prior to onset of manifestations. • New-onset livedo reticularis and/or palmar erythema at symptom onset. • Presence of any autoantibody and/or hypergammaglobulinemia and/or elevated ACE and/or elevated LDH and/or hypocomplementemia.
<p>Requirement: Presence of 2 major criteria, or 1 major + 2 minor, to diagnose ASIA.</p>	<p>Requirement: Presence of 3 major criteria, or 2 major + 2 minor, to diagnose ASIA.</p>

Table 1. Proposed criteria for establishing the diagnosis of adjuvant-induced autoimmune syndrome (ASIA). A) Diagnostic criteria for ASIA proposed by Shoenfeld and Agmon-Levin. B) New diagnostic criteria for human adjuvant disease or ASIA proposed by Alijotas-Reig.

From a clinical point of view, it presents with classic constitutional manifestations including myalgia, arthralgia, chronic fatigue, and dry mouth, as well as neurological manifestations such as cognitive impairment, memory loss, and neurological disabilities [6].

The therapeutic approach to this type of pathology is complex due to the various anatomical areas in which the modeling material infiltrates and the different techniques used. The approach will differ depending on the depth at which the material is placed [9].

Mucormycosis is a rare disease that is difficult to diagnose and has high morbidity and mortality rates. Diagnosis is often delayed, and the disease tends to progress rapidly. There are reports of cutaneous mucormycosis and also necrotizing fasciitis in immunocompetent patients. There are reports of cutaneous mucormycosis and also necrotizing fasciitis in immunocompetent patients. First-line therapy requires multidisciplinary management that includes control of the underlying condition, control of concomitant infections, surgery, and antifungal therapy. The antifungal of choice is liposomal amphotericin B as monotherapy. Cutaneous mucormycosis in young adult patients is uncommon, has an unusual clinical presentation, and should be suspected in previously established skin lesions exposed to any contaminated substances or objects [11].

CONCLUSION

The use of biopolymers in Mexico is a public health problem that has been on the rise over the years. According to the Ministry of Health, there are records of around 4,000 cases between 2002 and 2017 at the Dr. Eduardo Liceaga General Hospital of Mexico alone. Iatrogenic allogenesis is believed to be attributed to the fact that most of these procedures are performed by untrained personnel or non-physicians who are unaware of the serious consequences of introducing allogenic substances into the body, causing inflammatory and immunological reactions.

It is expected that new cases will develop in the future, which is why it is essential to understand the term “iatrogenic allogenesis” and “adjuvant-induced autoimmune syndrome.” There are well-founded clinical and serological criteria for timely diagnosis by physicians, especially family doctors, internists, and surgeons, as complications are irreversible and require multidisciplinary management in most cases.

As well as raising awareness and providing guidance to patients who have undergone or wish to undergo cosmetic procedures, informing them about the substances that can be used for these procedures, and which substances should not be used under any circumstances. This would help us prevent future complications, as we observed in the unfortunate outcome of this patient's case, who also developed a rare superinfection such as mucormycosis, which has a high mortality rate.

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